

Development of Multimedia Package in Teaching Geographical Concepts at Secondary Level

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ABSTRACT: This paper describes the development of multimedia package for geography. This paper argues for the development of multi-media package for secondary level students from different classes. Further, it has suggested that at school level the various program are made for teachers, students, trainees to integrate ICT and e- learning in the system of education, administration, learning, teaching, management, evaluation controlled by electronic media. As multimedia presentations is an important and use full for the dynamic subject like geography, researcher he selected the present research problem for the study.

Keywords: development, multimedia package, teaching, geographical concepts etc.

Introduction: Today's age is known as information communication technology age and it has an important aspect of the revolution of computer technology. Government's decision to introduce computer and the students of 1st to 12th standard is due to the need of ICT in teaching-learning process. Computer training is also included now a day in syllabus computer assisted teaching. Software's are widen the student's competency, computer education etc. are included in formal education.

Teaching is an art & science as well. It is a complicated process. Grasping and spreading of knowledge is very important in teaching – learning process. Human sensory organs have very important process of grasping the knowledge different type of senses reach to human brain through various sensory organs and hence these senses become meaning full. The various actions take place on them.

Grasping the knowledge is dependent on human beings sensory organ's strength. Each sensory organ has its own specific grasping power. These sensory organs are the places of acquiring knowledge. We remember for long time this experience only due to actual looking, hearing, touching or smelling the things.

II. Significance of the study: The significance of the present study is as follows:

1. The present research will be use full for all the elements of education and it will also contribute to the knowledge of teacher and students.
2. The present research will make teaching & learning more effective.
3. The present research study will increase the curiosity and interest among the teachers. It is also a path for the scholars in this area.

4. The present research is important to increase computer literacy in society.
5. The present research is helpful to increase student's audio and visual competency.
6. It will correlate the study in geography subject, concepts and related day today teaching.
7. The present research also important as the multimedia package, to be used to acquire the knowledge and the interest in geography subject.
8. The system will be helpful for the distance learning mode and in-service training.

III. Statement of the Problem: Development of Multimedia Package in Teaching Geographical Concepts at Secondary Level.

IV. Operational Definitions:

1. **Development:** The term development includes the planning, designing, constructing & testing of an instructional system.
2. **Multimedia E book:** A book designed for and dedicated on multimedia technology. It is an electronic book which includes visual imagery, text, video, sound and animation on the selected concepts of geography learning & teaching.
3. **Geography Subject:** A compulsory subject at secondary level.
4. **Secondary Level:** Linkage for primary and higher secondary level.

V. Objectives:

1. To study the problem while teaching geographical concept at the secondary level with traditional methods.
2. To develop multimedia package to teaching geographical concept at the secondary level.
3. To study the effectiveness of multimedia package in geographical concept at the secondary level.
4. To compare the effectiveness of traditional teaching method & teaching with multimedia package for geographical concept at the secondary level.

VI. Hypothesis:

- a) **Research Hypothesis:** There is significant difference geographical students' performance by teaching geographical concepts with the help of multimedia e book.
- b) **Null Hypothesis:**
 - 1: There is no significant difference between the performance of the students from control and experimental group in pre- test.
 - 2: There is no significant difference between the performance of the students from control and experimental group in post- test.
 - 3: There is no significant difference between the performances of the students from control group in pre over post- testing.
 - 4: There is no significant difference between the performances of the students from experimental group in pre over post testing.

VII. Scope and Limitations:

1. It is related only secondary level.
2. The present research is related only geographical concepts at the secondary level.

3. The present research is related to the development of Multimedia package to Marathi medium school only.
4. The study is limited to the some geographical concepts from geography subject at the secondary level.
5. The present research is limited only IX std. students only.
6. The development of multimedia package is included for designing, developing and evaluating stages.

VIII. Research Tools: Questionnaire, Pre- test, and Post - test.

Preparation of Tools: I. Questionnaire:

To find out the problem in traditional teaching method, the researcher will give the teaching geography subject at the secondary level. In this Questionnaire, the questions will be related to the problems while teaching geography subject.

II. Achievement Test (pre and post- test) related to geography subject:

Two tests i.e. pre and post- test prepared by the researcher geography subject in the present research. These tests covered basic knowledge in few geographical concepts for IX STD.

Each test consists of 20 items. These items were of multiple choice types. Each question carries 1 mark for correct alternative and 0 marks for incorrect alternative.

IX. Research Methodology: In present research the researcher has been used a survey and experimental method. The researcher made two equal groups for pre- post- test.

Research Procedure

i. Study the problems while teaching geographical concept; Survey:

The researcher, will survey the traditional teaching methods to teach geographical concepts, although researcher will find out the problems in traditional teaching method to teach geography subject. The researcher will give questionnaire to 30 teachers to teach geography subject for secondary level.

ii. Development and Implementation multimedia package by researcher:

The researcher will develop multimedia package with instructional system for geography subject of IX STD. To solve these problems in multimedia package there will be 5 concepts of geography subject.

X. Analysis and Interpretation of the Data:

Frequency distribution of total score obtained by students in the pre and post - test regarding effectiveness of multimedia package is as follows:

Table No. 1

Total score obtained by all student in Pre and Post Test

Observation and Interpretation:

Measure	Control group	Experimental group
Number of Student (N)	30	30
Mean (M)	9.43	12.13
S.D	1.22	1.91
D- Mean	2.7	
t value	6.525*	
df	58	

The findings are stated on the basis of null Hypothesis, there is no significant difference between two groups so null hypothesis should be rejected as the value is greater than the value at 0. 01 significance level is remarkable.

XI. Conclusions:

- The most of student have below average level of achievement in geography subject.
- The developed multimedia package related to geography subject was quite effective.
- The developed multimedia packages create the curiosity and interest among the learners.

XII. Recommendations:

1. The modern methods should be used for teaching geographical concepts.
2. The teaching of geography should be a creative work.
3. It is necessary to create proper learning atmosphere in class at secondary level.
4. Teacher should develop modern and recent methods for teaching geography subject.

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